

Versatility within (4,4) networks assembled from 1,4-bis(ⁿalkoxy)-2,5-bis(3,2':6',3''-terpyridin-4'-yl)benzene and [Cu(hfacac)₂] (Hhfacac = hexafluoropentane-2,4-dione)

Simona S. Capomolla, Giacomo Manfroni, Alessandro Prescimone, Edwin C. Constable and Catherine E. Housecroft*

Department of Chemistry, University of Basel, Mattenstrasse 24a, BPR 1096, 4058 Basel, Switzerland

Experimental Section

Ligand precursor syntheses

Compound **2a**

Compound **2a** has previously been reported,¹ but the following synthesis was found to be convenient. 2,5-Dibromobenzene-1,4-diol (4.00 g, 14.9 mmol, 1.0 eq), 1-bromoethane (4.0 mL, 52 mmol, 3.5 eq) and anhydrous K₂CO₃ (7.21 g, 52.2 mmol, 3.5 eq) were combined in dry DMF (80 mL) and the reaction mixture was heated and stirred at 100 °C for 21 h under N₂. The reaction mixture was then allowed to cool to room temperature, poured onto ice water (200 mL) and was stirred for 20 minutes. The resulting suspension was extracted with chloroform (3 x 150 mL). The organic layers were combined, dried over MgSO₄ and concentrated *in vacuo*. The crude product was recrystallized from a hot mixture of MeOH (15 mL) and CHCl₃ (15 mL). The red solution was allowed to slowly cool to -20 °C and was left to crystallize for 16 h. The resultant white crystals were collected by filtration, washed with MeOH and CHCl₃ and dried *in vacuo*. The filtrate was reduced to half its original volume and then cooled to -20 °C to yield a second crop of product which was collected by filtration, washed with MeOH and CHCl₃ and dried *in vacuo*. The two crops of product were combined to yield **2a** (4.29 g, 13.2 mmol, 88.9%) as off-white crystals. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): δ/ppm 7.10 (s, 2H, H³), 4.03 (q, *J* = 7.0 Hz, 4H, H^a), 1.44 (t, *J* = 7.0 Hz, 6H, H^b). ¹³C{¹H} NMR (126 MHz,

CDCl₃): δ /ppm 150.1 (C²), 118.8 (C³), 111.3 (C¹), 66.1 (C^a), 14.9 (C^b). The NMR spectroscopic data agreed with the literature [1].

Compound 3a

Compound **3a** has previously been reported [1], but the following synthesis is convenient. 2,5-Dibromobenzene-1,4-diol (4.00 g, 14.9 mmol, 1.0 eq), 1-bromopropane (4.7 mL, 52 mmol, 3.5 eq) and anhydrous K₂CO₃ (7.21 g, 52.2 mmol, 3.5 eq) were combined in dry DMF (80 mL) and the reaction mixture was heated to 100 °C and then stirred for 16 h under N₂. The reaction mixture was then allowed to cool to room temperature, poured onto ice water (200 mL) and was stirred for 20 minutes. The resulting suspension was extracted with chloroform (3 x 150 mL). The organic layers were combined, dried over MgSO₄ and concentrated *in vacuo*. The crude product was recrystallized from a hot mixture of MeOH (15 mL) and CHCl₃ (10 mL). The red solution was allowed to slowly cool to room temperature and was left to crystallize for 16 h. The resultant crystals were collected by filtration, washed with MeOH and CHCl₃ and dried *in vacuo*. The filtrate was reduced to half its original volume and then cooled to -20 °C to yield a second crop of crystalline product which was collected by filtration, washed with MeOH and CHCl₃ and dried *in vacuo*. The two crops of product were combined to yield **3a** (4.28 g, 12.2 mmol, 81.6%) as off-white crystals. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): δ /ppm 7.09 (s, 2H, H³), 3.92 (t, *J* = 6.5 Hz, 4H, H^a), 1.83 (dtd, *J* = 13.8, 7.4, 6.4 Hz, 4H, H^b), 1.06 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 6H, H^c). ¹³C{¹H} NMR (126 MHz, CDCl₃): δ /ppm 150.2 (C²), 118.7 (C³), 111.3 (C¹), 71.9 (C^a), 22.7 (C^b), 10.7 (C^c). The NMR spectroscopic data agreed with the literature [1].

Compound 4a

Compound **4a** has previously been reported [1], but the following synthesis is convenient. 2,5-Dibromobenzene-1,4-diol (4.00 g, 14.9 mmol, 1.0 eq), 1-bromobutane (5.6 mL, 52 mmol, 3.5 eq) and anhydrous K₂CO₃ (7.21 g, 52.2 mmol, 3.5 eq) were combined in dry DMF (100 mL) and the reaction mixture was stirred at 100 °C for 16 h under N₂. The reaction mixture was then allowed to cool to room temperature, poured onto ice water (200 mL) and was stirred for 20 minutes. The resulting suspension was extracted with chloroform (3 x 150 mL). The organic layers were combined, dried over MgSO₄ and concentrated *in vacuo*. The crude product was recrystallized from a hot mixture of EtOH (10 mL) and MeOH (2 mL). The red solution was allowed to slowly cool to room temperature and was left to crystallize for 16 h. The resultant crystals were collected by filtration, washed with EtOH and dried *in vacuo*. The filtrate was reduced to half its original volume and cooled to -20 °C to yield a second crop of crystalline product. The resultant crystals were again collected by filtration, washed with EtOH

and dried *in vacuo*. The two crops of product were combined to yield **4a** (4.58 g, 12.1 mmol, 80.9%) as pale-red crystals. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3): δ /ppm 7.09 (s, 2H, H^3), 3.96 (t, $J = 6.5$ Hz, 4H, H^a), 1.79 (ddt, $J = 8.9, 7.7, 6.3$ Hz, 4H, H^b), 1.57 – 1.45 (m, 4H, H^c), 0.98 (t, $J = 7.4$ Hz, 6H, H^d). $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (126 MHz, CDCl_3): δ /ppm 150.2 (C^2), 118.6 (C^3), 111.3 (C^1), 70.2 (C^a), 31.4 (C^b), 19.4 (C^c), 14.0 (C^d). The NMR spectroscopic data agreed with the literature [1].

Compound **5a**

2,5-Dibromobenzene-1,4-diol (4.00 g, 14.9 mmol, 1.0 eq), 1-bromopentane (6.5 mL, 52 mmol, 3.5 eq) and anhydrous K_2CO_3 (7.21 g, 52.2 mmol, 3.5 eq) were combined in dry DMF (100 mL) under N_2 and the reaction mixture was heated to 100 °C and then stirred for 16 h. The reaction mixture was then allowed to cool to room temperature, poured onto ice water (200 mL) and was stirred for 20 minutes. The resulting suspension was extracted with chloroform (3 x 150 mL). The organic layers were combined, dried over MgSO_4 and concentrated *in vacuo*. The crude product was reprecipitated from a hot EtOH (10 mL) solution. The red solution was allowed to slowly cool to room temperature under mild stirring to reprecipitate for 16 h. The resultant solid was collected by filtration, washed with EtOH and dried *in vacuo* to yield **5a** (3.76 g, 9.21 mmol, 61.8%) as pale-red solid. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3): δ /ppm 7.09 (s, 2H, H^3), 3.95 (t, $J = 6.5$ Hz, 4H, H^a), 1.81 (dq, $J = 8.1, 6.5$ Hz, 4H, H^b), 1.50 – 1.43 (m, 4H, H^c), 1.43 – 1.35 (m, 4H, H^d), 0.94 (t, $J = 7.2$ Hz, 6H, H^e). $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (126 MHz, CDCl_3): δ /ppm 150.2 (C^2), 118.6 (C^3), 111.3 (C^1), 70.5 (C^a), 29.0 (C^b), 28.3 (C^c), 22.5 (C^d), 14.2 (C^e).

Compound **6a**

The synthesis of **6a** has previously been reported [2], but the following method is convenient. 2,5-Dibromobenzene-1,4-diol (4.00 g, 14.9 mmol, 1.0 eq), 1-bromohexane (7.4 mL, 52 mmol, 3.5 eq) and anhydrous K_2CO_3 (7.21 g, 52.2 mmol, 3.5 eq) were combined in dry DMF (100 mL) under N_2 and the reaction mixture was heated to 100 °C and stirred for 19 h. The reaction mixture was then allowed to cool to room temperature, poured onto ice water (200 mL) and was stirred for 20 minutes. The resulting suspension was extracted with chloroform (3 x 150 mL). The organic layers were combined, dried over MgSO_4 and concentrated *in vacuo*. The crude product was reprecipitated under stirring from a hot EtOH (10 mL) solution over 16 h. The resultant precipitate was collected by filtration, washed with EtOH and dried *in vacuo*. The filtrate was reduced to half its original volume and then cooled to 0 °C to yield a second crop of precipitate which was collected by filtration, washed with EtOH and dried *in vacuo*. The crops of **6a** were combined (pale-red solid, 5.43 g, 12.4 mmol, 83.5%). ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3): δ /ppm 7.08 (s, 2H, H^3), 3.95 (t, $J = 6.5$ Hz, 4H, H^a), 1.80 (ddt, $J = 9.1, 7.9, 6.5$ Hz, 4H, H^b),

1.52 – 1.43 (m, 4H, H^c), 1.38 – 1.31 (overlapping m, 8H, H^{d+e}), 0.91 (t, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 6H, H^f). ¹³C{¹H} NMR (126 MHz, CDCl₃): δ/ppm 150.2 (C²), 118.6 (C³), 111.3 (C¹), 70.5 (C^a), 31.6 (C^d), 29.2 (C^b), 25.8 (C^c), 22.7 (C^e), 14.2 (C^f). The NMR spectroscopic data agreed with the literature [2].

Compound **7a**

Compound **7a** has previously been reported [3], but the following synthesis is convenient. 2,5-Dibromobenzene-1,4-diol (4.00 g, 14.9 mmol, 1.0 eq), 1-bromoheptane (8.2 mL, 52 mmol, 3.5 eq) and anhydrous K₂CO₃ (7.21 g, 52.2 mmol, 3.5 eq) were combined in dry DMF (100 mL) and the reaction mixture was stirred at 100 °C for 16 h under N₂. The reaction mixture was then allowed to cool to room temperature, poured onto ice water (200 mL) and was stirred for 20 minutes. The resulting suspension was extracted with chloroform (3 x 150 mL). The organic layers were combined, dried over MgSO₄ and concentrated *in vacuo*. The crude product was reprecipitated under gentle stirring from a hot EtOH (10 mL) solution over 16 h. The resultant precipitate was collected by filtration, washed with EtOH and dried *in vacuo* to yield **7a** (5.30 g, 11.4 mmol, 76.6%) as a pale-red solid. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): δ/ppm 7.08 (s, 2H, H³), 3.94 (t, *J* = 6.5 Hz, 4H, H^a), 1.80 (dq, *J* = 7.9, 6.6 Hz, 4H, H^b), 1.51 – 1.42 (m, 4H, H^c), 1.42 – 1.23 (overlapping m, 12H, H^{d+e+f}), 0.89 (t, *J* = 7.0 Hz, 4H, H^g). ¹³C{¹H} NMR (126 MHz, CDCl₃): δ/ppm 150.2 (C²), 118.6 (C³), 111.3 (C¹), 70.5 (C^a), 31.9 (C^e), 29.3 (C^b), 29.1 (C^d), 26.1 (C^c), 22.7 (C^f), 14.2 (C^g). The NMR spectroscopic data agreed with the literature [3].

Compound **2b**

The preparation of **2b** has previously been reported [1], but the following method is convenient. Compound **2a** (1.50 g, 4.63 mmol, 1.0 eq) was dissolved in dry Et₂O (100 mL) and the solution was cooled to 0 °C under N₂. ⁿBuLi (15% in hexanes, 1.6 M, 11.6 mL, 18.5 mmol, 4.0 eq) was added at 0 °C over a period of 15 min and the reaction mixture was stirred at 0 °C for 2 h. Dry DMF (1.4 mL, 19 mmol, 4.0 eq) was added and the reaction mixture was stirred for 20 h, allowing the mixture to slowly warm from 0 °C to room temperature (ca. 22 °C). The now light yellow suspension was quenched by the addition of saturated aqueous NH₄Cl (150 mL) and subsequently extracted with chloroform (3 x 100 mL). The organic layers were combined, dried over MgSO₄ and concentrated *in vacuo*. The crude product was purified by column chromatography (silica, EtOAc in cyclohexane 2–18% gradient) yielding **2b** (411 mg, 1.85 mmol, 39.9%) as a yellow crystalline solid. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): δ/ppm 10.52 (s, 2H, H^{CHO}), 7.43 (s, 2H, H³), 4.17 (q, *J* = 7.0 Hz, 4H, H^a), 1.46 (t, *J* = 7.0 Hz, 6H, H^b). ¹³C{¹H} NMR (126

MHz, CDCl₃): δ /ppm 189.6 (C^{CHO}), 155.2 (C²), 129.4 (C¹), 111.8 (C³), 65.0 (C^a), 14.8 (C^b). The NMR spectroscopic data agreed with the literature [1].

Compound **3b**

The synthesis of **3b** has previously been reported [1] but the following method is convenient. Compound **3a** (2.00 g, 5.68 mmol, 1.0 eq) was dissolved in dry Et₂O (100 mL) and the solution was cooled to 0 °C under N₂. ⁿBuLi (15% in hexanes, 1.6 M, 14.2 mL, 22.7 mmol, 4.0 eq) was added at 0 °C over a period of 15 min and the reaction mixture was stirred at 0 °C for 2 h. Dry DMF (1.8 mL, 23 mmol, 4.0 eq) was added and the reaction mixture was stirred at 0 °C for 1 h. The now light yellow suspension was quenched by the addition of saturated aqueous NH₄Cl (150 mL) and subsequently extracted with chloroform (3 x 100 mL). The organic layers were combined, dried over MgSO₄ and concentrated *in vacuo*. The crude material was purified by column chromatography (silica, EtOAc in cyclohexane 0–20% gradient). After removal of solvent from the fraction collected, the yellow solid was recrystallized from petroleum ether (25 mL). The yellow solution was allowed to slowly cool to room temperature and was left to crystallize for 18 h. The resultant crystals were collected by filtration, washed with petroleum ether and dried *in vacuo*. The filtrate was cooled to –20 °C to yield a second crop of crystalline product which was collected by filtration, washed with petroleum ether and dried *in vacuo*. The product crops were combined to give **3b** (729 mg, 2.91 mmol, 51.3%) as a yellow crystalline solid. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): δ /ppm 10.53 (s, 2H, H^{CHO}), 7.43 (s, 2H, H³), 4.06 (t, *J* = 6.5 Hz, 4H, H^a), 1.93 – 1.82 (m, 4H, H^b), 1.06 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 6H, H^c). ¹³C{¹H} NMR (126 MHz, CDCl₃): δ /ppm 189.6 (C^{CHO}), 155.4 (C²), 129.5 (C¹), 111.8 (C³), 70.9 (C^a), 22.6 (C^b), 10.7 (C^c). The NMR spectroscopic data agreed with the literature [1].

Compound **4b**

The synthesis of **4b** has been reported [1], but the following method is convenient. Compound **4a** (2.00 g, 5.26 mmol, 1.0 eq) was dissolved in dry Et₂O (100 mL) and the solution was cooled to 0 °C under N₂. ⁿBuLi (15% in hexanes, 1.6 M, 13.1 mL, 21.0 mmol, 4.0 eq) was added at 0 °C over a period of 15 min and the reaction mixture was stirred at 0 °C for 2 h. Dry DMF (1.6 mL, 21 mmol, 4.0 eq) was added and the reaction mixture was stirred at 0 °C for 1 h. The now light yellow suspension was quenched by the addition of saturated aqueous NH₄Cl (150 mL) and subsequently extracted with chloroform (3 x 100 mL). The organic layers were combined, dried over MgSO₄ and concentrated *in vacuo*. The crude product was purified by column

chromatography (silica, EtOAc in cyclohexane 0–20% gradient). The yellow product was recrystallized from petroleum ether (15 mL) and the yellow solution was allowed to slowly cool to room temperature and was left to crystallize for 18 h. The resultant crystals were collected by filtration, washed with petroleum ether and dried *in vacuo*. The filtrate was reduced to half its original volume and then cooled to $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to yield a second crop of crystalline product which was collected by filtration, washed with petroleum ether and dried *in vacuo*. The product crops were combined to give **4b** (657 mg, 2.36 mmol, 44.9%) as a fine, light-yellow crystalline solid. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3): δ /ppm 10.52 (s, 2H, H^{CHO}), 7.43 (s, 2H, H^3), 4.10 (t, $J = 6.4$ Hz, 4H, H^{a}), 1.82 (ddt, $J = 9.0, 7.7, 6.4$ Hz, 4H, H^{b}), 1.54 – 1.47 (m, 4H, H^{c}), 0.99 (t, $J = 7.4$ Hz, 6H, H^{d}). $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (126 MHz, CDCl_3): δ /ppm 189.6 (C^{CHO}), 155.4 (C^2), 129.4 (C^1), 111.8 (C^3), 69.1 (C^{a}), 31.2 (C^{b}), 19.4 (C^{c}), 13.9 (C^{d}). The NMR spectroscopic data agreed with previously reported values.⁵⁴

Compound 5b

Compound **5a** (2.50 g, 6.12 mmol, 1.0 eq) was dissolved in dry Et_2O (100 mL) and the solution was cooled to $0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ under N_2 . $^n\text{BuLi}$ (15% in hexanes, 1.6 M, 15.3 mL, 24.5 mmol, 4.0 eq) was added at $0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ over a period of 15 min and the reaction mixture was stirred at $0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 2 h. Dry DMF (1.9 mL, 25 mmol, 4.0 eq) was added and the reaction mixture was stirred at $0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 1 h. The now light yellow suspension was quenched by the addition of saturated aqueous NH_4Cl (150 mL) and subsequently extracted with chloroform (3 x 100 mL). The organic layers were combined, dried over MgSO_4 and concentrated *in vacuo*. The crude product was purified by column chromatography (silica, EtOAc in cyclohexane 0–13% gradient). The yellow product was recrystallized from petroleum ether (15 mL) over a period of 18 h. The resultant crystals were collected by filtration, washed with petroleum ether and dried *in vacuo*. The filtrate was reduced to half its original volume and then cooled to $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to yield a second crop of crystalline product which was collected by filtration, washed with petroleum ether and dried *in vacuo*. Overall, **5b** was obtained as a pale-yellow crystalline solid (309 mg, 1.01 mmol, 16.5%). ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3): δ /ppm 10.52 (s, 2H, H^{CHO}), 7.43 (s, 2H, H^3), 4.09 (t, $J = 6.5$ Hz, 4H, H^{a}), 1.84 (dq, $J = 7.9, 6.5$ Hz, 4H, H^{b}), 1.51 – 1.31 (overlapping m, 8H, $\text{H}^{\text{c+d}}$), 0.94 (t, $J = 7.2$ Hz, 6H, H^{e}). $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (126 MHz, CDCl_3): δ /ppm 189.6 (C^{CHO}), 155.4 (C^2), 129.4 (C^1), 111.8 (C^3), 69.4 (C^{a}), 28.9 (C^{b}), 28.3 (C^{c}), 22.5 (C^{d}), 14.1 (C^{e}).

Compound 6b

Compound **6b** has previously been reported [4], but the following is a convenient method. Compound **6a** (2.00 g, 4.58 mmol, 1.0 eq) was dissolved in dry Et₂O (100 mL) and the solution was cooled to 0 °C under N₂. ⁿBuLi (15% in hexanes, 1.6 M, 11.5 mL, 18.3 mmol, 4.0 eq) was added at 0 °C over a period of 15 min and the reaction mixture was stirred at 0 °C for 2 h. Dry DMF (1.4 mL, 18 mmol, 4.0 eq) was added and the reaction mixture was stirred for 20 h, allowing the mixture to slowly warm from 0 °C to room temperature. The now light yellow suspension was quenched by the addition of saturated aqueous NH₄Cl (150 mL) and subsequently extracted with chloroform (3 x 100 mL). The organic layers were combined, dried over MgSO₄ and concentrated *in vacuo*. The crude product was recrystallized from petroleum ether (6 mL), with the yellow solution being allowed to slowly cool to room temperature over a period of 72 h. The resultant crystals were collected by filtration, washed with petroleum ether and dried *in vacuo* to give **6b** (373 mg, 1.12 mmol, 24.4%) as a yellow crystalline solid. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): δ/ppm 10.52 (s, 2H, H^{CHO}), 7.43 (s, 2H, H³), 4.09 (t, *J* = 6.5 Hz, 4H, H^a), 1.83 (ddt, *J* = 9.1, 7.8, 6.5 Hz, 4H, H^b), 1.52 – 1.42 (m, 4H, H^c), 1.39 – 1.29 (overlapping m, 8H, H^{d+e}), 0.91 (t, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 6H, H^f). ¹³C{¹H} NMR (126 MHz, CDCl₃): δ/ppm 189.6 (C^{CHO}), 155.4 (C²), 129.4 (C¹), 111.8 (C³), 69.4 (C^a), 31.6 (C^d), 29.2 (C^b), 25.8 (C^e), 22.7 (C^e), 14.1 (C^f). The NMR spectroscopic data agreed with the literature [4].

Compound 7b

Compound **7b** has previously been reported [5], but the following synthesis is convenient. Compound **7a** (1.84 g, 3.96 mmol, 1.0 eq) was dissolved in dry Et₂O (100 mL) and the solution was cooled to 0 °C under N₂. ⁿBuLi (15% in hexanes, 1.6 M, 9.9 mL, 16 mmol, 4.0 eq) was added at 0 °C over a period of 15 min and the reaction mixture was stirred at 0 °C for 2 h. Dry DMF (1.2 mL, 16 mmol, 4.0 eq) was added and the reaction mixture was stirred for 18 h, allowing the mixture to slowly warm from 0 °C to room temperature. The now light yellow suspension was quenched by the addition of saturated aqueous NH₄Cl (150 mL) and subsequently extracted with chloroform (3 x 100 mL). The organic layers were combined, dried over MgSO₄ and concentrated *in vacuo*. The crude product was purified by column chromatography (silica, EtOAc in cyclohexane 0–13% gradient). The yellow product was recrystallized from petroleum ether (4 mL) and the resultant crystals were collected by filtration, washed with petroleum ether and dried *in vacuo* to give **7b** (260 mg, 0.717 mmol, 18.1%) as a yellow crystalline solid. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): δ/ppm 10.52 (s, 2H, H^{CHO}), 7.43 (s, 2H, H³), 4.09 (t, *J* = 6.5 Hz, 4H, H^a), 1.87 – 1.79 (m, 4H, H^b), 1.51 – 1.43 (m, 4H, H^c), 1.40 – 1.28 (overlapping m, 12H, H^{d+e+f}), 0.90 (t, *J* = 6.9 Hz, 6H, H^g). ¹³C{¹H} NMR (126 MHz, CDCl₃): δ/ppm 189.6 (C^{CHO}), 155.4 (C²), 129.4 (C¹), 111.8 (C³), 69.4 (C^a), 31.9 (C^e), 29.2 (C^b), 29.1 (C^d), 26.1 (C^c), 22.7 (C^f), 14.2 (C^g). The NMR spectroscopic data agreed with the literature [5].

General procedure for the synthesis of the bis(3,2':6',3''-terpyridine) ligands

The appropriate 2,5-dialkyloxybenzene-1,4-dicarbaldehyde (1.0 eq) was placed at room temperature in EtOH (25–50 mL). 3-Acetylpyridine (5.0 eq) and crushed KOH (5.0 eq) were then added. Immediate color change upon the addition of KOH from yellow to orange/red observed. Then slow addition of aqueous NH₃ solution (32%, 120 eq) followed and the reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 21-96 h. The fine precipitate that formed was collected by filtration and washed with H₂O (3 x 7-15 mL), followed by EtOH (3 x 7-15 mL) and Et₂O (2x 7-15 mL) and then dried *in vacuo*. The off-white/ light yellow crude solid was recrystallized/ reprecipitated from a mixture of EtOH and CHCl₃, MeOH and CHCl₃ or EtOH to give the desired bis(3,2':6',3''-terpyridine) ligand.

Compound 1

2,5-Dimethoxybenzene-1,4-dicarbaldehyde (850 mg, 4.38 mmol, 1.0 eq), 3-acetylpyridine (2.4 mL, 22 mmol, 5.0 eq), crushed KOH (1.23 g, 21.9 mmol, 5.0 eq) and aqueous NH₃ solution (32%, 65 mL) were combined in EtOH (50 mL) according to the general procedure and the reaction mixture was stirred for 21 h. The pale-yellow product was reprecipitated by the addition of EtOH (ca. 2 mL) to a CHCl₃ (ca. 30 mL) solution of the crude material. The suspension was left to precipitate at 5 °C for 72 h. The resultant precipitate was collected by filtration, washed with EtOH and dried *in vacuo* to give **1** (609 mg, 1.01 mmol, 23.1%) as a white solid. Decomposition > 333.1 °C. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): δ/ppm 9.37 (d, *J* = 2.3 Hz, 4H, H^{A2}), 8.72 (dd, *J* = 4.8, 1.7 Hz, 4H, H^{A6}), 8.53 (dt, *J* = 8.0, 2.0 Hz, 4H, H^{A4}), 8.00 (s, 4H, H^{B3}), 7.48 (dd, *J* = 7.9, 4.8 Hz, 4H, H^{A5}), 7.16 (s, 2H, H^{C3}), 3.92 (s, 6H, H^a). ¹³C{¹H} NMR (126 MHz, CDCl₃): δ/ppm 155.1 (C^{B2}), 151.1 (C^{C2}), 150.4 (C^{A6}), 148.6 (C^{A2}), 148.1 (C^{C1}), 134.9 (C^{A3}), 134.7 (C^{A4}), 129.2 (C^{B4}), 123.8 (C^{A5}), 120.3 (C^{B3}), 114.3 (C^{C3}), 56.8 (C^a). UV-Vis (CHCl₃, 2 x 10⁻⁵ mol dm⁻³) λ/nm 277 sh (ε/dm⁻³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ 47,730), 315 (21,510), 353 sh (11,790). MALDI-TOF-MS *m/z* 601.23 [M+H]⁺ (calc. 601.24). Found C 75.22, H 4.61, N 13.97; required for C₃₈H₂₈N₆O₂ C 75.98, H 4.70, N 13.99.

Compound 2

Compound **2b** (320 mg, 1.44 mmol, 1.0 eq), 3-acetylpyridine (790 μL , 7.2 mmol, 5.0 eq), crushed KOH (404 mg, 7.20 mmol, 5.0 eq) and aqueous NH_3 solution (32%, 21 mL) were combined in EtOH (25 mL) according to the general procedure and the reaction mixture was stirred for 72 h. The off-white product was dissolved in MeOH (12 mL) and CHCl_3 (3 mL) under reflux. The solution was then concentrated until precipitation started and was then placed in a refrigerator (5 $^\circ\text{C}$) for 16 h. The precipitate that formed was collected by filtration, washed with MeOH and dried *in vacuo* to give the **2** (242 mg, 0.384 mmol, 26.7%) as a white solid. Decomposition > 299.5 $^\circ\text{C}$. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3): δ /ppm 9.37 (dd, $J = 2.3, 0.9$ Hz, 4H, $\text{H}^{\text{A}2}$), 8.71 (dd, $J = 4.8, 1.7$ Hz, 4H, $\text{H}^{\text{A}6}$), 8.53 (dt, $J = 8.0, 1.9$ Hz, 4H, $\text{H}^{\text{A}4}$), 8.04 (s, 4H, $\text{H}^{\text{B}3}$), 7.48 (ddd, $J = 7.9, 4.8, 0.9$ Hz, 4H, $\text{H}^{\text{A}5}$), 7.18 (s, 2H, $\text{H}^{\text{C}3}$), 4.15 (q, $J = 7.0$ Hz, 4H, H^{a}), 1.43 (t, $J = 6.9$ Hz, 6H, H^{b}). $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (126 MHz, CDCl_3): δ /ppm 155.3 ($\text{C}^{\text{B}2}$), 150.9 ($\text{C}^{\text{C}2}$), 150.6 ($\text{C}^{\text{A}6}$), 148.9 ($\text{C}^{\text{A}2}$), 148.4 ($\text{C}^{\text{C}1}$), 135.3 ($\text{C}^{\text{A}3}$), 135.0 ($\text{C}^{\text{A}4}$), 129.7 ($\text{C}^{\text{B}4}$), 124.1 ($\text{C}^{\text{A}5}$), 120.6 ($\text{C}^{\text{B}3}$), 115.8 ($\text{C}^{\text{C}3}$), 65.7 (C^{a}), 15.5 (C^{b}). UV-Vis (CHCl_3 , 2×10^{-5} mol dm^{-3}) λ/nm 277 sh (ϵ/dm^{-3} mol $^{-1}$ cm $^{-1}$ 48,100), 314 (20,120), 355 sh (11,610). MALDI-TOF-MS m/z 629.30 [$\text{M}+\text{H}$] $^+$ (calc. 629.27). Found C 75.11, H 5.02, N 13.24; required for $\text{C}_{40}\text{H}_{32}\text{N}_6\text{O}_2 \cdot 0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ C 75.33, H 5.22, N 13.18. HR-ESI MS m/z 629.2656 [$\text{M}+\text{H}$] $^+$ (calc. 629.2660).

Compound 3

Compound **3b** (720 mg, 2.89 mmol, 1.0 eq), 3-acetylpyridine (1.6 mL, 15 mmol, 5.0 eq), crushed KOH (811 mg, 14.5 mmol, 5.0 eq) and aqueous NH_3 solution (32%, 42 mL) were combined in EtOH (50 mL) according to the general procedure and the reaction mixture was

stirred for 72 h. The crude product was recrystallized from a hot EtOH (10 mL) and CHCl₃ (3 mL) solution by allowing the yellow solution to cool to room temperature for 18 h. The crystals that formed were collected by filtration, washed with EtOH and dried *in vacuo* to give **3** (421 mg, 0.642 mmol, 22.2%) as a light-yellow crystalline solid. M.p. 276.4–278.3 °C. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): δ/ppm 9.38 (dd, *J* = 2.4, 0.9 Hz, 4H, H^{A2}), 8.71 (dd, *J* = 4.8, 1.6 Hz, 4H, H^{A6}), 8.54 (ddd, *J* = 8.0, 2.3, 1.7 Hz, 4H, H^{A4}), 8.04 (s, 4H, H^{B3}), 7.48 (ddd, *J* = 7.9, 4.7, 0.9 Hz, 4H, H^{A5}), 7.17 (s, 2H, H^{C3}), 4.04 (t, *J* = 6.5 Hz, 4H, H^a), 1.81 (dtd, *J* = 13.8, 7.4, 6.4 Hz, 4H, H^b), 0.98 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 6H, H^c). ¹³C{¹H} NMR (126 MHz, CDCl₃): δ/ppm 154.9 (C^{B2}), 150.7 (C^{C2}), 150.3 (C^{A6}), 148.5 (C^{A2}), 148.1 (C^{C1}), 134.9 (C^{A3}), 134.6 (C^{A4}), 129.4 (C^{B4}), 123.8 (C^{A5}), 120.3 (C^{B3}), 115.4 (C^{C3}), 71.4 (C^a), 22.9 (C^b), 10.8 (C^c). UV-Vis (CHCl₃, 2 x 10⁻⁵ mol dm⁻³) λ/nm 277 sh (ε/dm⁻³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ 46,600), 314 (19,520), 355 sh (11,290). MALDI-TOF-MS *m/z* 657.22 [M+H]⁺ (calc. 657.30). Found C 75.54, H 5.46, N 12.61; required for C₄₂H₃₆N₆O₂·0.5H₂O C 75.77, H 5.60, N 12.62. HR-ESI MS *m/z* 657.2970 [M+H]⁺ (calc. 657.2973).

Compound 4

Compound **4b** (650 mg, 2.34 mmol, 1.0 eq), 3-acetylpyridine (1.3 mL, 12 mmol, 5.0 eq), crushed KOH (656 mg, 11.7 mmol, 5.0 eq) and aqueous NH₃ solution (32%, 34 mL) were combined in EtOH (50 mL) according to the general procedure and the reaction mixture was stirred for 72 h. The crude product was recrystallized from a hot mixture of EtOH (12 mL) and CHCl₃ (3 mL). The yellow solution was allowed to cool to room temperature and was left to crystallize for 18 h. The resultant crystals were collected by filtration, washed with EtOH and dried *in vacuo* to give **4** (429 mg, 0.627 mmol, 26.8%) as a pale-yellow crystalline solid. M.p. 227.2–231.2 °C. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): δ/ppm 9.38 (dd, *J* = 2.3, 0.9 Hz, 4H, H^{A2}), 8.72 (dd, *J* = 4.8, 1.7 Hz, 4H, H^{A6}), 8.53 (ddd, *J* = 8.0, 2.3, 1.7 Hz, 4H, H^{A4}), 8.03 (s, 4H, H^{B3}), 7.48 (ddd, *J* = 7.9, 4.8, 0.9 Hz, 4H, H^{A5}), 7.17 (s, 2H, H^{C3}), 4.07 (t, *J* = 6.4 Hz, 4H, H^a), 1.76 (ddt, *J* = 9.1, 7.9, 5.9 Hz, 4H, H^b), 1.50 – 1.37 (m, 4H, H^c), 0.87 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 6H, H^d). ¹³C{¹H} NMR (126 MHz, CDCl₃): δ/ppm 154.9 (C^{B2}), 150.7 (C^{C2}), 150.4 (C^{A6}), 148.5 (C^{A2}), 148.1 (C^{C1}), 134.9 (C^{A3}), 134.6 (C^{A4}), 129.4 (C^{B4}), 123.8 (C^{A5}), 120.3 (C^{B3}), 115.3 (C^{C3}), 69.5 (C^a), 31.5 (C^b), 19.5 (C^c), 13.8 (C^d). UV-Vis (CHCl₃, 2 x 10⁻⁵ mol dm⁻³) λ/nm 277 sh (ε/dm⁻³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ 49,580), 315 (20,640), 356 sh (11,950). MALDI-TOF-MS *m/z* 685.25 [M+H]⁺ (calc. 685.33). Found C 76.76, H 5.83, N 12.55; required for C₄₄H₄₀N₆O₂ C 77.17, H 5.89, N 12.27.

Compound 5

Compound **5b** (280 mg, 914 μmol , 1.0 eq), 3-acetylpyridine (500 μL , 4.6 mmol, 5.0 eq), crushed KOH (256 mg, 4.57 mmol, 5.0 eq) and aqueous NH_3 solution (32%, 13 mL) were combined in EtOH (25 mL) according to the general procedure and the reaction mixture was stirred for 90 h. The crude product was recrystallized from a hot EtOH (3 mL) solution by allowing the light-yellow solution to cool to room temperature and left to stand for 18 h. The crystals that formed were collected by filtration, washed with EtOH and dried *in vacuo* to give **5** (159 mg, 223 μmol , 24.4% yield) as a white crystalline solid. M.p. 203.0–205.0 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3): δ /ppm 9.38 (dd, $J = 2.3, 0.9$ Hz, 4H, $\text{H}^{\text{A}2}$), 8.72 (dd, $J = 4.7, 1.7$ Hz, 4H, $\text{H}^{\text{A}6}$), 8.53 (ddd, $J = 8.0, 2.3, 1.7$ Hz, 4H, $\text{H}^{\text{A}4}$), 8.03 (s, 4H, $\text{H}^{\text{B}3}$), 7.48 (ddd, $J = 7.9, 4.7, 0.9$ Hz, 4H, $\text{H}^{\text{A}5}$), 7.17 (s, 2H, $\text{H}^{\text{C}3}$), 4.06 (t, $J = 6.4$ Hz, 4H, H^{a}), 1.81–1.70 (m, 4H, H^{b}), 1.42–1.32 (m, 4H, H^{c}), 1.31–1.20 (m, 4H, H^{d}), 0.76 (t, $J = 7.2$ Hz, 6H, H^{e}). $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (126 MHz, CDCl_3): δ /ppm 154.9 ($\text{C}^{\text{B}2}$), 150.7 ($\text{C}^{\text{C}2}$), 150.4 ($\text{C}^{\text{A}6}$), 148.6 ($\text{C}^{\text{A}2}$), 148.1 ($\text{C}^{\text{C}1}$), 134.9 ($\text{C}^{\text{A}3}$), 134.6 ($\text{C}^{\text{A}4}$), 129.4 ($\text{C}^{\text{B}4}$), 123.8 ($\text{C}^{\text{A}5}$), 120.4 ($\text{C}^{\text{B}3}$), 115.4 ($\text{C}^{\text{C}3}$), 69.9 (C^{a}), 29.2 (C^{b}), 28.5 (C^{c}), 22.5 (C^{d}), 14.0 (C^{e}). UV-Vis (CHCl_3 , 2×10^{-5} mol dm^{-3}) λ/nm 277 sh (ϵ/dm^{-3} mol $^{-1}$ cm $^{-1}$ 46,800), 313 (19,300), 356 sh (11,160). MALDI-TOF-MS m/z 713.28 $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$ (calc. 713.36). Found C 74.48, H 6.35, N 11.47; required for $\text{C}_{46}\text{H}_{44}\text{N}_6\text{O}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ C 73.77, H 6.46, N 11.22. HR-ESI MS m/z 713.3589 $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$ (calc. 713.3599).

Compound 6

Compound **6b** (360 mg, 1.08 mmol, 1.0 eq), 3-acetylpyridine (600 μL , 5.4 mmol, 5.0 eq), crushed KOH (303 mg, 5.40 mmol, 5.0 eq) and aqueous NH_3 solution (32%, 16 mL) were combined in EtOH (15 mL) according to the general procedure, and the reaction mixture was stirred for 72 h. The crude product was recrystallized from a hot EtOH (3 mL) solution by

allowing the light-yellow solution to cool to room temperature and leaving it to crystallize for 72 h. The crystals that formed were collected by filtration, washed with EtOH and dried *in vacuo* to give **6** (181 mg, 0.244 mmol, 22.6% yield) as a light-yellow crystalline solid. M.p. 187.7 – 189.4 °C. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): δ/ppm 9.38 (dd, *J* = 2.3, 0.9 Hz, 4H, H^{A2}), 8.71 (dd, *J* = 4.8, 1.7 Hz, 4H, H^{A6}), 8.53 (dt, *J* = 7.9, 1.9 Hz, 4H, H^{A4}), 8.03 (s, 4H, H^{B3}), 7.48 (ddd, *J* = 8.0, 4.8, 0.9 Hz, 4H, H^{A5}), 7.17 (s, 2H, H^{C3}), 4.06 (t, *J* = 6.4 Hz, 4H, H^a), 1.79 – 1.71 (m, 4H, H^b), 1.37 (ddd, *J* = 15.3, 8.3, 6.4 Hz, 4H, H^c), 1.27 – 1.10 (overlapping m, 8H, H^{d+e}), 0.75 (t, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 6H, H^f). ¹³C{¹H} NMR (126 MHz, CDCl₃): δ/ppm 154.9 (C^{B2}), 150.7 (C^{C2}), 150.3 (C^{A6}), 148.6 (C^{A2}), 148.2 (C^{C1}), 134.9 (C^{A3}), 134.6 (C^{A4}), 129.4 (C^{B4}), 123.8 (C^{A5}), 120.4 (C^{B3}), 115.4 (C^{C3}), 69.9 (C^a), 31.6 (C^d), 29.5 (C^b), 26.1 (C^c), 22.6 (C^e), 14.0 (C^f). UV-Vis (CHCl₃, 2 × 10⁻⁵ mol dm⁻³) λ/nm 277 sh (ε/dm⁻³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ 48,020), 314 (20,400), 356 sh (11,100). MALDI-TOF-MS *m/z* 741.43 [M+H]⁺ (calc. 741.39). Found C 77.05, H 6.60, N 11.16; required for C₄₈H₄₈N₆O₂ C 77.81, H 6.53, N 11.34.

Compound 7

Compound **7b** (250 mg, 747 μmol, 1.0 eq), 3-acetylpyridine (410 μL, 3.7 mmol, 5.0 eq), crushed KOH (145 mg, 3.74 mmol, 5.0 eq) and aqueous NH₃ solution (32%, 11 mL) were combined in EtOH (15 mL) according to the general procedure and the reaction mixture was stirred for 70 h. The crude product was recrystallized from a hot EtOH (3 mL) solution by leaving the light-yellow solution to cool to room temperature and standing for 72 h. The resultant crystals were collected by filtration, washed with EtOH and dried *in vacuo* to give **7** (201 mg, 261 μmol, 34.9% yield) as an off-white crystalline solid. M.p. 191.3 – 193.1 °C. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): δ/ppm 9.38 (dd, *J* = 2.4, 0.9 Hz, 4H, H^{A2}), 8.71 (dd, *J* = 4.8, 1.7 Hz, 4H, H^{A6}), 8.53 (dt, *J* = 7.9, 2.0 Hz, 4H, H^{A4}), 8.03 (s, 4H, H^{B3}), 7.47 (ddd, *J* = 8.0, 4.7, 0.9 Hz, 4H, H^{A5}), 7.17 (s, 2H, H^{C3}), 4.06 (t, *J* = 6.3 Hz, 4H, H^a), 1.79 – 1.71 (m, 4H, H^b), 1.41 – 1.31 (m, 4H, H^c), 1.25 – 1.06 (overlapping m, 12H, H^{d+e+f}), 0.77 (t, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 6H, H^g). ¹³C{¹H} NMR (126 MHz, CDCl₃): δ/ppm 154.9 (C^{B2}), 150.7 (C^{C2}), 150.3 (C^{A6}), 148.6 (C^{A2}), 148.1 (C^{C1}), 134.9 (C^{A3}), 134.6 (C^{A4}), 129.5 (C^{B4}), 123.8 (C^{A5}), 120.3 (C^{B3}), 115.4 (C^{C3}), 69.9 (C^a), 31.8 (C^e), 29.6 (C^b), 29.1 (C^d), 26.4 (C^c), 22.6 (C^f), 14.1 (C^g). UV-Vis (CHCl₃, 2 × 10⁻⁵ mol dm⁻³) λ/nm 277 sh (ε/dm⁻³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ 46,790), 314 (19,560), 356 sh (11,090). MALDI-TOF-MS *m/z* 769.50 [M+H]⁺ (calc. 769.42). Found C 75.92, H 6.70, N 10.77; required for C₅₀H₅₂N₆O₂·H₂O C 76.31, H 6.92, N 10.68. HR-ESI MS *m/z* 769.4217 [M+H]⁺ (calc. 769.4225).

Crystal growth conditions and crystallographic data

Compound **6b**

X-ray quality crystals were grown from cooling of a hot petroleum ether solution of **6b**.

$C_{20}H_{30}O_4$, $M_r = 334.44$, yellow block, triclinic, space group $P\bar{1}$, $a = 8.3418(3)$, $b = 10.6492(3)$, $c = 11.7555(3)$ Å, $\alpha = 110.529(2)$, $\beta = 103.839(2)$, $\gamma = 96.260(2)^\circ$, $V = 927.96(5)$ Å³, $D_c = 1.197$ g cm⁻³, $T = 150$ K, $Z = 2$, $\mu(\text{GaK}\alpha) = 0.417$ mm⁻¹, 12412 reflections measured, 3559 unique ($R_{\text{int}} = 0.0327$). Refinement of 3328 reflections (220 parameters) with $I > 2\sigma(I)$ converged at final $R_1 = 0.0462$ (R_1 all data = 0.0484), $wR_2 = 0.1251$ (wR_2 all data = 0.1282), $\text{gof} = 1.036$. CCDC 2156091.

$[Cu_2(\text{hfacac})_4(\mathbf{1})]_n \cdot 3nCHCl_3$

An EtOH (5 mL) solution of $[Cu(\text{hfacac})_2] \cdot H_2O$ (9.9 mg, 20 μmol) was layered over a $CHCl_3$ solution (4 mL) of ligand **1** (6.0 mg, 10 μmol). Green block-like crystals grew after 28 days and one was selected for single crystal X-ray diffraction. Only one crystal was of X-ray quality. The remaining bulk material was analyzed by PXRD.

$C_{30.50}H_{17.50}Cl_{4.50}CuF_{12}N_3O_5$, $M_r = 957.04$, green block, triclinic, space group $P\bar{1}$, $a = 8.8255(6)$, $b = 15.0003(9)$, $c = 17.2031(10)$ Å, $\alpha = 94.709(5)$, $\beta = 101.652(5)$, $\gamma = 97.170(5)^\circ$, $V = 2199.5(2)$ Å³, $D_c = 1.445$ g cm⁻³, $T = 150$ K, $Z = 2$, $\mu(\text{CuK}\alpha) = 4.030$ mm⁻¹, 35634 reflections measured, 8167 unique ($R_{\text{int}} = 0.0728$). Refinement of 5890 reflections (459 parameters) with $I > 2\sigma(I)$ converged at final $R_1 = 0.1497$ (R_1 all data = 0.1691), $wR_2 = 0.3617$ (wR_2 all data = 0.3773), $\text{gof} = 1.058$. CCDC 2156094.

$[Cu_2(\text{hfacac})_4(\mathbf{2})]_n \cdot 1.2nCHCl_3$

A MeOH (5 mL) solution of $[Cu(\text{hfacac})_2] \cdot H_2O$ (9.9 mg, 20 μmol) was layered over a $CHCl_3$ solution (4 mL) of ligand **2** (6.3 mg, 10 μmol). Green block-shaped crystals grew after 38 days and one X-ray quality crystal was chosen. The remaining crystals were analyzed by PXRD and FT-IR spectroscopy.

$C_{30.60}H_{18.60}Cl_{1.8}CuF_{12}N_3O_5$, $M_r = 863.63$, green block, triclinic, space group $P\bar{1}$, $a = 9.7533(5)$, $b = 11.5305(6)$, $c = 16.7007(7)$ Å, $\alpha = 93.926(4)$, $\beta = 97.867(4)$, $\gamma = 106.571(4)^\circ$, $V = 1771.75(15)$ Å³, $D_c = 1.619$ g cm⁻³, $T = 150$ K, $Z = 2$, $\mu(\text{CuK}\alpha) = 3.102$ mm⁻¹, 25329 reflections measured, 6533 unique ($R_{\text{int}} = 0.0474$). Refinement of 6384 reflections (454 parameters) with $I > 2\sigma(I)$ converged at final $R_1 = 0.1479$ (R_1 all data = 0.1496), $wR_2 = 0.3503$ (wR_2 all data = 0.3515), $\text{gof} = 1.041$. CCDC 2156083.

$[Cu_2(\text{hfacac})_4(\mathbf{2})_2]_n \cdot 1.5nCHCl_3 \cdot 4nMeOH$

A MeOH (5 mL) solution of $[Cu(\text{hfacac})_2] \cdot H_2O$ (9.9 mg, 20 μmol) was layered over a $CHCl_3$ solution (4 mL) of ligand **2** (6.3 mg, 10 μmol). Green plate-shaped crystals grew after 24 days and a single crystal was selected for X-ray diffraction. The remaining crystals were analyzed by PXRD and FT-IR spectroscopy.

$C_{105.50}H_{85.50}Cl_{4.50}Cu_2F_{24}N_{12}O_{16}$, $M_r = 2519.96$, green plate, orthorhombic, space group $Pca2_1$, $a = 32.8471(5)$, $b = 11.19310(10)$, $c = 15.2802(2)$ Å, $V = 5617.93(12)$ Å³, $D_c = 1.490$ g cm⁻³, $T = 150$ K, $Z = 2$, $\mu(\text{CuK}\alpha) = 2.401$ mm⁻¹, 48310 reflections measured, 6642 unique ($R_{\text{int}} = 0.0381$). Refinement of 6118 reflections (791 parameters) with $I > 2\sigma(I)$ converged at final $R_1 = 0.0594$ (R_1 all data = 0.0639), $wR_2 = 0.1776$ (wR_2 all data = 0.1690), $\text{gof} = 1.079$. CCDC 2156086.

[Cu₂(hfacac)₄(3)]_n·5.5nC₆H₅Cl

A chlorobenzene (5 mL) solution of [Cu(hfacac)₂]₂·H₂O (19.8 mg, 40.0 μmol) was layered over a CHCl₃ solution (4 mL) of ligand **3** (13.1 mg, 20.0 μmol). Green plate-shaped crystals grew after 30 days and a single crystal was selected for X-ray diffraction. The remaining crystals were analyzed by PXRD and FT-IR spectroscopy.

C₉₅H_{67.50}Cl_{5.50}Cu₂F₂₄N₆O₁₀, *M_r* = 2231.10, green plate, triclinic, space group *P*-1, *a* = 17.1968(5), *b* = 17.1866(5), *c* = 19.5179(5) Å, *α* = 85.835(2), *β* = 85.830(2), *γ* = 69.549(2)°, *V* = 5383.8(3) Å³, *D_c* = 1.376 g cm⁻³, *T* = 150 K, *Z* = 2, *μ*(GaK_α) = 3.518 mm⁻¹, 75111 reflections measured, 20559 unique (*R*_{int} = 0.0741). Refinement of 13161 reflections (852 parameters) with *I* > 2σ(*I*) converged at final *R*₁ = 0.1202 (*R*₁ all data = 0.1552), *wR*₂ = 0.3084 (*wR*₂ all data = 0.3400), *gof* = 1.018. CCDC 2156097.

[Cu₂(hfacac)₄(4)]_n·3.5nC₆H₄Cl₂

A solution of [Cu(hfacac)₂]₂·H₂O (9.9 mg, 20 μmol) in MeOH (5 mL) was layered over a 1,2-dichlorobenzene solution (4 mL) of ligand **4** (6.9 mg, 10 μmol). Green plate-shaped crystals grew after 47 days and one X-ray quality crystal was chosen. The remaining crystals were analyzed by PXRD and FT-IR spectroscopy.

C₈₅H₅₈Cl₇Cu₂F₂₄N₆O₁₀, *M_r* = 2154.60, green plate, triclinic, space group *P*-1, *a* = 8.86900(10), *b* = 16.0659(2), *c* = 33.1531(5) Å, *α* = 81.2720(10), *β* = 86.1880(10), *γ* = 81.0180(10)°, *V* = 4607.54(11) Å³, *D_c* = 1.553 g cm⁻³, *T* = 150 K, *Z* = 2, *μ*(CuK_α) = 3.400 mm⁻¹, 83211 reflections measured, 17852 unique (*R*_{int} = 0.0320). Refinement of 12466 reflections (1044 parameters) with *I* > 2σ(*I*) converged at final *R*₁ = 0.0913 (*R*₁ all data = 0.1043), *wR*₂ = 0.2705 (*wR*₂ all data = 0.2873), *gof* = 1.080. CCDC 2156096.

[Cu₂(hfacac)₄(4)]_n·4nMeC₆H₅

A solution of [Cu(hfacac)₂]₂·H₂O (9.9 mg, 20 μmol) in MeOH (5 mL) was layered over a toluene solution (4 mL) of ligand **4** (6.9 mg, 10 μmol). Green plate-shaped crystals grew after 26 days and a single crystal was selected for X-ray diffraction. The remaining crystals were analyzed by PXRD and FT-IR spectroscopy.

C₉₂H₇₆Cu₂F₂₄N₆O₁₀, *M_r* = 2008.66, green plate, triclinic, space group *P*-1, *a* = 8.45360(10), *b* = 20.9041(3), *c* = 26.2349(4) Å, *α* = 88.5590(10), *β* = 81.2140(10), *γ* = 80.3140(10)°, *V* = 4516.38(11) Å³, *D_c* = 1.477 g cm⁻³, *T* = 150 K, *Z* = 2, *μ*(CuK_α) = 1.563 mm⁻¹, 70316 reflections measured, 16652 unique (*R*_{int} = 0.0217). Refinement of 16239 reflections (1166 parameters) with *I* > 2σ(*I*) converged at final *R*₁ = 0.0561 (*R*₁ all data = 0.0568), *wR*₂ = 0.1485 (*wR*₂ all data = 0.1491), *gof* = 1.042. CCDC 2156084.

[Cu₃(hfacac)₆(5)₂]_n grown from MeOH and toluene

A solution of [Cu(hfacac)₂]₂·H₂O (9.9 mg, 20 μmol) in MeOH (5 mL) was layered over a toluene solution (4 mL) of ligand **5** (7.1 mg, 10 μmol). Green plate-shaped crystals grew after 20 days and a single crystal was selected for X-ray diffraction. The remaining crystals were analyzed by PXRD and FT-IR spectroscopy.

C₁₂₂H₉₄Cu₃F₃₆N₁₂O₁₆, *M_r* = 2858.71, green plate, monoclinic, space group *P*2₁/*c*, *a* = 11.9727(2), *b* = 37.6012(4), *c* = 14.5251(2) Å, *β* = 102.3690(10)°, *V* = 6387.24(16) Å³, *D_c* = 1.486 g cm⁻³, *T* = 150 K, *Z* = 2, *μ*(CuK_α) = 1.638 mm⁻¹, 64460 reflections measured, 12029 unique (*R*_{int} = 0.0469). Refinement of 10455 reflections (878 parameters) with *I* > 2σ(*I*) converged at final *R*₁ = 0.1412 (*R*₁ all data = 0.1493), *wR*₂ = 0.3548 (*wR*₂ all data = 0.3653), *gof* = 1.072. CCDC 2156087.

[Cu₃(hfacac)₆(5)₂]_n grown from MeOH and CHCl₃

A solution of [Cu(hfacac)₂]₂·H₂O (9.9 mg, 20 μmol) in MeOH (5 mL) was layered over a CHCl₃ solution (4 mL) of ligand **5** (7.1 mg, 10 μmol). Green plate-shaped crystals grew after 36 days and a single crystal was selected for X-ray diffraction. The remaining crystals were analyzed by PXRD and FT-IR spectroscopy.

C₆₁H₄₇Cu_{1.50}F₁₈N₆O₈, *M_r* = 1429.35, green block, monoclinic, space group *P*2₁/*c*, *a* = 11.96060(10), *b* = 37.6107(5), *c* = 14.5313(2) Å, β = 102.3980(10)°, *V* = 6384.41(14) Å³, *D_c* = 1.487 g cm⁻³, *T* = 150 K, *Z* = 4, μ(CuKα) = 1.639 mm⁻¹, 58328 reflections measured, 12004 unique (*R*_{int} = 0.0460). Refinement of 10513 reflections (877 parameters) with *I* > 2σ(*I*) converged at final *R*₁ = 0.1186 (*R*₁ all data = 0.1278), *wR*₂ = 0.2682 (*wR*₂ all data = 0.2763), *gof* = 1.149. CCDC 2156085.

[Cu₂(hfacac)₄(5)]_n·3.5nC₆H₄Cl₂

A solution of [Cu(hfacac)₂]₂·H₂O (9.9 mg, 20 μmol) in MeOH (5 mL) was layered over a 1,2-dichlorobenzene solution (4 mL) of ligand **5** (7.1 mg, 10 μmol). Green block-shaped crystals grew after 36 days and a single crystal was selected for X-ray diffraction. The remaining crystals were analyzed by PXRD and FT-IR spectroscopy.

C_{43.50}H₃₁Cl_{3.50}CuF₁₂N₃O₅, *M_r* = 1091.33, green block, triclinic, space group *P*-1, *a* = 10.7222(2), *b* = 11.5435(2), *c* = 19.9016(4) Å, α = 103.5550(10), β = 92.089(2), γ = 95.216(2)°, *V* = 2380.48(8) Å³, *D_c* = 1.523 g cm⁻³, *T* = 150 K, *Z* = 2, μ(GaKα) = 4.221 mm⁻¹, 37632 reflections measured, 9128 unique (*R*_{int} = 0.0774). Refinement of 8265 reflections (582 parameters) with *I* > 2σ(*I*) converged at final *R*₁ = 0.1295 (*R*₁ all data = 0.1352), *wR*₂ = 0.3031 (*wR*₂ all data = 0.3073), *gof* = 1.045. CCDC 2156088.

[Cu₂(hfacac)₄(6)]_n·2.4nMeC₆H₅

A solution of [Cu(hfacac)₂]₂·H₂O (9.9 mg, 20 μmol) in MeOH (5 mL) was layered over a toluene solution (4 mL) of ligand **6** (7.4 mg, 10 μmol). Green block-shaped crystals grew after 27 days and a single crystal was selected for X-ray diffraction. The remaining crystals were analyzed by PXRD and FT-IR spectroscopy.

C_{84.80}H_{71.20}Cu₂F₂₄N₆O₁₀, *M_r* = 1917.35, green block, triclinic, space group *P*-1, *a* = 8.7380(3), *b* = 15.7726(5), *c* = 16.3690(5) Å, α = 100.925(2), β = 91.399(2), γ = 98.053(2)°, *V* = 2190.24(12) Å³, *D_c* = 1.454 g cm⁻³, *T* = 150 K, *Z* = 1, μ(GaKα) = 3.252 mm⁻¹, 29952 reflections measured, 8361 unique (*R*_{int} = 0.0624). Refinement of 7308 reflections (566 parameters) with *I* > 2σ(*I*) converged at final *R*₁ = 0.0982 (*R*₁ all data = 0.1046), *wR*₂ = 0.2331 (*wR*₂ all data = 0.2381), *gof* = 0.940. CCDC 2156095.

[Cu₂(hfacac)₄(7)]_n·2.4nCHCl₃

A solution of [Cu(hfacac)₂]₂·H₂O (9.9 mg, 20 μmol) in MeOH (5 mL) was layered over a CHCl₃ solution (4 mL) of ligand **7** (7.7 mg, 10 μmol). Green block-shaped crystals grew after 24 days and a single crystal was selected for X-ray diffraction. The remaining crystals were analyzed by PXRD and FT-IR spectroscopy.

C_{36.20}H_{29.20}Cl_{3.60}CuF₁₂N₃O₅, *M_r* = 1005.38, green block, triclinic, space group *P*-1, *a* = 9.1948(2), *b* = 15.3447(4), *c* = 16.4286(4) Å, α = 78.318(2), β = 89.464(2), γ = 82.994(2)°, *V* = 2252.69(10) Å³, *D_c* = 1.482 g cm⁻³, *T* = 150 K, *Z* = 2, μ(GaKα) = 4.460 mm⁻¹, 35207 reflections measured, 8614 unique (*R*_{int} = 0.0529). Refinement of 7702 reflections (536 parameters) with *I* > 2σ(*I*) converged at final *R*₁ = 0.1035 (*R*₁ all data = 0.1086), *wR*₂ = 0.2510 (*wR*₂ all data = 0.2552), *gof* = 0.981. CCDC 2156089.

[Cu₂(hfacac)₄(7)]_n·2.6nCHCl₃ (polymorph A) grown from EtOH and CHCl₃

A solution of [Cu(hfacac)₂]₂·H₂O (9.9 mg, 20 μmol) in EtOH (5 mL) was layered over a CHCl₃ solution (4 mL) of ligand **7** (7.7 mg, 10 μmol). Green block-shaped crystals grew after 20 days and a single crystal was selected for X-ray diffraction. The remaining crystals were analyzed by PXRD and FT-IR spectroscopy.

C_{36.30}H_{30.30}Cl_{3.90}Cu₂F₁₂N₃O₅, *M_r* = 1018.33, green block, triclinic, space group *P*-1, *a* = 9.2226(2), *b* = 15.4810(4), *c* = 16.4057(4) Å, *α* = 78.237(2), *β* = 89.584(2), *γ* = 81.594(2)°, *V* = 2267.89(10) Å³, *D_c* = 1.491 g cm⁻³, *T* = 150 K, *Z* = 2, *μ*(GaK_α) = 4.541 mm⁻¹, 36672 reflections measured, 8579 unique (*R*_{int} = 0.0375). Refinement of 7683 reflections (548 parameters) with *I* > 2σ(*I*) converged at final *R*₁ = 0.0793 (*R*₁ all data = 0.0846), *wR*₂ = 0.2338 (*wR*₂ all data = 0.2423), *gof* = 1.042. CCDC 2156090.

[Cu₂(hfacac)₄(7)]_n·2.6nCHCl₃ (polymorph B) grown from ^tBuOH and CHCl₃

A ^tBuOH (5 mL) solution of [Cu(hfacac)₂]₂·H₂O (9.9 mg, 20 μmol) was layered over a CHCl₃ solution (4 mL) of ligand **7** (7.7 mg, 10 μmol). Green block-shaped crystals grew after 6 days and one X-ray quality crystal was chosen. The remaining crystals were analyzed by PXRD and FT-IR spectroscopy.

C_{72.60}H_{58.60}Cl_{7.80}Cu₂F₂₄N₆O₁₀, *M_r* = 2034.64, green prism, triclinic, space group *P*-1, *a* = 9.18180(10), *b* = 15.4587(3), *c* = 16.3294(2) Å, *α* = 101.1490(10), *β* = 89.9160(10), *γ* = 97.3970(10)°, *V* = 2254.45(6) Å³, *D_c* = 1.499 g cm⁻³, *T* = 150 K, *Z* = 1, *μ*(CuK_α) = 3.646 mm⁻¹, 39370 reflections measured, 8342 unique (*R*_{int} = 0.0337). Refinement of 7107 reflections (530 parameters) with *I* > 2σ(*I*) converged at final *R*₁ = 0.1133 (*R*₁ all data = 0.1233), *wR*₂ = 0.2512 (*wR*₂ all data = 0.2587), *gof* = 0.964. CCDC 2156092.

[Cu₂(hfacac)₄(7)]_n·2nMeC₆H₅

A MeOH (5 mL) solution of [Cu(hfacac)₂]₂·H₂O (9.9 mg, 20 μmol) was layered over a toluene solution (4 mL) of ligand **7** (7.7 mg, 10 μmol). Green block-shaped crystals grew after 24 days and a single crystal was selected for X-ray diffraction. The remaining crystals were analyzed by PXRD and FT-IR spectroscopy.

C₁₆₈H₁₄₄Cu₄F₄₈N₁₂O₂₀, *M_r* = 3817.10, green block, triclinic, space group *P*-1, *a* = 16.5084(2), *b* = 18.6500(2), *c* = 29.7291(4) Å, *α* = 95.0370(10), *β* = 96.0860(10), *γ* = 98.9960(10)°, *V* = 8938.59(19) Å³, *D_c* = 1.418 g cm⁻³, *T* = 150 K, *Z* = 2, *μ*(CuK_α) = 1.547 mm⁻¹, 155926 reflections measured, 34452 unique (*R*_{int} = 0.0357). Refinement of 27194 reflections (2089 parameters) with *I* > 2σ(*I*) converged at final *R*₁ = 0.1170 (*R*₁ all data = 0.1321), *wR*₂ = 0.2664 (*wR*₂ all data = 0.2778), *gof* = 1.158. CCDC 2156093.

[Cu₂(hfacac)₄(8)]_n·1.6nCHCl₃

A EtOH (5 mL) solution of [Cu(hfacac)₂]₂·H₂O (9.9 mg, 20 μmol) was layered over a CHCl₃ solution (4 mL) of ligand **8** (8.0 mg, 10 μmol). Green block-shaped crystals grew within 3 months and a single crystal was selected for X-ray diffraction. The remaining crystals were analyzed by PXRD and FT-IR spectroscopy.

C_{73.60}H_{61.60}Cl_{4.80}Cu₂F₂₄N₆O₁₀, *M_r* = 1943.32, green block, triclinic, space group *P*-1, *a* = 8.75610(10), *b* = 17.3784(2), *c* = 31.3635(4) Å, *α* = 103.9650(10), *β* = 90.1860(10), *γ* = 100.3980(10)°, *V* = 4549.89(10) Å³, *D_c* = 1.418 g cm⁻³, *T* = 150 K, *Z* = 2, *μ*(CuK_α) = 2.795 mm⁻¹, 145849 reflections measured, 17744 unique (*R*_{int} = 0.0425). Refinement of 14587 reflections (992 parameters) with *I* > 2σ(*I*) converged at final *R*₁ = 0.1015 (*R*₁ all data = 0.1119), *wR*₂ = 0.2434 (*wR*₂ all data = 0.2521), *gof* = 0.998. CCDC 2164225.

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Supplementary Figures

Figures S1–S24: NMR spectra of compounds 2a–7a and 2b–7b.

Figures S25–S35: Mass spectra of compounds 1–7

Figures S36–S63: NMR spectra of compounds 1–7

Figures S64–S70: IR spectra of compounds 1–7

Figures S71–S83: Structural figures and PXRD

Figure S1: ^1H NMR spectrum (500 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of **2a**. * = CHCl_3 , § = H_2O

Figure S2: $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum (126 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of **2a**. * = CDCl_3

Figure S3: ^1H NMR spectrum (500 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of **3a**. * = CHCl_3 , § = H_2O

Figure S4: $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum (126 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of **3a**. * = CDCl_3

Figure S5: ^1H NMR spectrum (500 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of **4a**. * = CHCl_3 , § = H_2O

Figure S6: $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum (126 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of **4a**. * = CDCl_3

Figure S7: ^1H NMR spectrum (500 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of **5a**. * = CHCl_3 , § = H_2O

Figure S8: $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum (126 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of **5a**. * = CDCl_3

Figure S9: ^1H NMR spectrum (500 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of **6a**. * = CHCl_3 , ζ = H_2O

Figure S10: $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum (126 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of **6a**. * = CDCl_3

Figure S11: ^1H NMR spectrum (500 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of **7a**. * = CHCl_3 , § = H_2O

Figure S12: $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum (126 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of **7a**. * = CDCl_3

Figure S13: ^1H NMR spectrum (500 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of **2b**. * = CHCl_3 , σ = H_2O

Figure S14: $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum (126 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of **2b**. * = CDCl_3

Figure S15: ^1H NMR spectrum (500 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of **3b**. * = CHCl_3 , § = H_2O

Figure S16: $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum (126 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of **3b**. * = CDCl_3

Figure S17: ^1H NMR spectrum (500 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of **4b**. * = CHCl_3 , § = H_2O

Figure S18: $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum (126 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of **4b**. * = CDCl_3

Figure S19: ^1H NMR spectrum (500 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of **5b**. * = CHCl_3 , § = H_2O

Figure S20: $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum (126 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of **5b**. * = CDCl_3

Figure S21: ^1H NMR spectrum (500 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of **6b**. * = CHCl_3 , σ = H_2O

Figure S22: $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum (126 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of **6b**. * = CDCl_3

Figure S23: ^1H NMR spectrum (500 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of **7b**. * = CHCl_3 , § = H_2O

Figure S24: $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum (126 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of **7b**. * = CDCl_3

Figure S25: The MALDI-TOF mass spectrum of ligand **1**, and expansion of the base peak.

Figure S26: The MALDI-TOF mass spectrum of ligand **2**, and expansion of the base peak.

Figure S27: The MALDI-TOF mass spectrum of ligand **3**, and expansion of the base peak.

Figure S28: The MALDI-TOF mass spectrum of ligand **4**, and expansion of the base peak.

Figure S29: The MALDI-TOF mass spectrum of ligand **5**, and expansion of the base peak.

Figure S3014: The MALDI-TOF mass spectrum of ligand **6**, and expansion of the base peak.

Figure S31: The MALDI-TOF mass spectrum of ligand **7**, and expansion of the base peak.

Figure S33: HR-ESI mass spectrum of ligand **3** comparing the experimental isotope pattern for the base peak arising from $[M+H]^+$ (top) with the calculated isotope pattern (bottom).

Figure S34: HR-ESI mass spectrum of ligand **5** comparing the experimental isotope pattern for the base peak arising from $[M+H]^+$ (top) with the calculated isotope pattern (bottom).

Figure S35: HR-ESI mass spectrum of ligand **7** comparing the experimental isotope pattern for the base peak arising from $[M+H]^+$ (top) with the calculated isotope pattern (bottom).

Figure S36: ^1H NMR spectrum (500 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of ligand **1**. * = CHCl_3 , § = H_2O

Figure S37: $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum (126 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of ligand **1**. * = CDCl_3

Figure S38: HMBC spectrum (^1H 500 MHz, $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ 126 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of ligand 1. * = CHCl_3 , ** = CDCl_3 , § = H_2O

Figure S39: HMBC spectrum (^1H 500 MHz, $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ 126 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of ligand 1. * = CHCl_3 , ** = CDCl_3 , § = H_2O

Figure S40: ^1H NMR spectrum (500 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of ligand **2**. * = CHCl_3 , § = H_2O

Figure S41: $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum (126 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of ligand **2**. * = CDCl_3

Figure S4416: ^1H NMR spectrum (500 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of ligand **3**. * = CHCl_3 , § = H_2O

Figure S4517: $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum (126 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of ligand **3**. * = CDCl_3

Figure S4618: HMBC spectrum (^1H 500 MHz, $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ 126 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of ligand **3**. * = CHCl_3 , ** = CDCl_3 , § = H_2O

Figure S47: HMBC spectrum (^1H 500 MHz, $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ 126 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of ligand **3**. * = CHCl_3 , ** = CDCl_3 , § = H_2O

Figure S48: ^1H NMR spectrum (500 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of ligand **4**. * = CHCl_3 , § = H_2O

Figure S49: $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum (126 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of ligand **4**. * = CDCl_3

Figure S5019: HMBC spectrum (^1H 500 MHz, $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ 126 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of ligand 4. * = CHCl_3 , ** = CDCl_3 , § = H_2O

Figure S51: HMBC spectrum (^1H 500 MHz, $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ 126 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of ligand 4. * = CHCl_3 , ** = CDCl_3 , § = H_2O

Figure S52: ¹H NMR spectrum (500 MHz, CDCl₃, 298 K) of ligand 5. * = CHCl₃, § = H₂O

Figure S53: ¹³C{¹H} NMR spectrum (126 MHz, CDCl₃, 298 K) of ligand 5. * = CDCl₃

Figure S54: HMBC spectrum (^1H 500 MHz, $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ 126 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of ligand **5**. * = CHCl_3 , ** = CDCl_3 , § = H_2O

Figure S55: HMBC spectrum (^1H 500 MHz, $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ 126 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of ligand **5**. * = CHCl_3 , ** = CDCl_3 , § = H_2O

Figure S5620: ¹H NMR spectrum (500 MHz, CDCl₃, 298 K) of ligand **6**. * = CHCl₃, § = H₂O

Figure S5721: ¹³C{¹H} NMR spectrum (126 MHz, CDCl₃, 298 K) of ligand **6**. * = CDCl₃

Figure S60: ^1H NMR spectrum (500 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of ligand **7**. * = CHCl_3

Figure S6122: $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum (126 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of ligand **7**. * = CDCl_3

Figure S62: HMOC spectrum (^1H 500 MHz, $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ 126 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of ligand 7. * = CHCl_3 , ** = CDCl_3

Figure S63: HMBC spectrum (^1H 500 MHz, $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ 126 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of ligand 7. * = CHCl_3 , ** = CDCl_3

Figure S64: The solid state FT-IR spectrum of ligand 1.

Figure S65: The solid state FT-IR spectrum of ligand 2.

Figure S66: The solid state FT-IR spectrum of ligand 3.

Figure S67: The solid state FT-IR spectrum of ligand 4.

Figure S68: The solid state FT-IR spectrum of ligand 5.

Figure S69: The solid state FT-IR spectrum of ligand 6.

Figure S70: The solid state FT-IR spectrum of ligand 7.

Figure S71. The structure of the asymmetric unit in $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{hfacac})_4(\mathbf{1})]_n \cdot 3n\text{CHCl}_3$ with symmetry generated atoms. Hydrogen atoms are omitted for clarity; ellipsoids are plotted at 50% probability level. Symmetry codes: $i = -1+x, y, 1+z$; $ii = -x, -y, 1-z$; $iii = -1+x, -1+y, z$; $iv = 1-x, 1-y, 1-z$; $v = 1-x, -y, -z$. The CF_3 groups with C22, C24, C28 and C31 are disordered and only the major or one of the equal occupancy sites is shown.

Figure S72. The structure of the asymmetric unit in $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{hfacac})_4(\mathbf{2})]_n \cdot 1.2n\text{CHCl}_3$ with symmetry generated atoms. Hydrogen atoms are omitted for clarity; ellipsoids are plotted at 50% probability level. Symmetry codes: $i = x, -1+y, 1+z$; $ii = 1-x, -y, 2-z$; $iii = 1+x, -1+y, z$; $iv = -x, 1-y, 2-z$. The CF_3 groups with C25, C30 and C32 are disordered and only the major occupancy site is shown.

Figure S73. The structure of the asymmetric unit in $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{hfacac})_4(\mathbf{4})]_n \cdot 3.5n\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl}_2$. Hydrogen atoms are omitted for clarity; ellipsoids are plotted at 50% probability level.

Figure S74. The structure of the asymmetric unit in $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{hfacac})_4(\mathbf{4})]_n \cdot 4n\text{MeC}_6\text{H}_5$, with symmetry generated atoms. Hydrogen atoms are omitted for clarity; ellipsoids are plotted at 50% probability level. Symmetry codes: $i = 2-x, -y, -z$; $ii = 2-x, -y, 1-z$; $iii = 1-x, 1-y, 1-z$; $iv = 1-x, 1-y, -z$; $v = x, y, -1+z$; $vi = x, y, 1+z$. The CF_3 groups with C5 and C9 were refined isotropically and are also disordered; they have been modelled over sites of 50:50% occupancies, and only one occupancy site is shown.

Figure S75. The structure of the asymmetric unit in $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{hfacac})_4(\mathbf{5})]_n \cdot 3.5n\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl}_2$ with symmetry generated atoms. Hydrogen atoms are omitted for clarity; ellipsoids are plotted at 50% probability level. Symmetry codes: $i = 1+x, -1+y, z$; $ii = 2-x, -y, -z$; $iii = x, -1+y, -1+z$; $iv = 1-x, 1-y, -z$; $v = 2-x, 1-y, 1-z$.

Figure S76. The structure of the asymmetric unit in $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{hfacac})_4(\mathbf{6})]_n \cdot 2.4n\text{MeC}_6\text{H}_5$, with symmetry generated atoms. Hydrogen atoms are omitted for clarity; ellipsoids are plotted at 50% probability level. Symmetry codes: $i = x, y, -1+z$; $ii = 1-x, -y, -z$; $iii = -1+x, -1+y, z$; $iv = 1-x, -y, 1-z$; $v = 2-x, 1-y, -z$. The CF_3 group with C38, and the $[\text{hfacac}]^-$ group with O1 and O2 are disordered with 50:50% site occupancies, and only one of the occupancies is shown.

Figure S77. The structure of the asymmetric unit in $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{hfacac})_4(\mathbf{7})]_n \cdot 2.6n\text{CHCl}_3$, with symmetry generated atoms. Hydrogen atoms are omitted for clarity; ellipsoids are plotted at 50% probability level. Symmetry codes: $i = -1+x, -1+y, z$; $ii = 1-x, 1-y, 1-z$; $iii = x, y, -1+z$; $iv = 2-x, 2-y, 1-z$; $v = 1-x, 1-y, 2-z$. The $[\text{hfacac}]^-$ group with O1 and O2 is disordered over two equal occupancy sites and only one is shown. The terminal units with C24 and C25 in the $-\text{OHeptyl}$ chain are disordered and have been modelled over sites of 75% and 25% occupancies and only the major one is shown. The CF_3 group with C35 was refined isotropically.

Figure S78. The structure of the asymmetric unit in $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{hfacac})_4(\mathbf{8})]_n \cdot 1.6n\text{CHCl}_3$. Hydrogen atoms are omitted for clarity; ellipsoids are plotted at 50% probability level. The terminal parts of both $-\text{OOctyl}$ chains are disordered; the chain attached to O3 has been modelled with site occupancies 60:40% and the chain attached to O4 has been modelled over equal occupancy sites. The CF_3 groups with C71, C75 and C76 are rotationally disordered and each has been modelled over sites of 60:40%.

Figure S79. The structure of the asymmetric unit in $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{hfacac})_4(\mathbf{3})]_n \cdot 5.5n\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{Cl}$, with symmetry generated atoms. Hydrogen atoms are omitted for clarity; ellipsoids are plotted at 50% probability level. Symmetry codes: i = $1-x, -y, -z$; ii = $x, y, -1+z$; iii = $-x, 1-y, 1-z$; iv = $-x, 1-y, -z$; v = $x, y, 1+z$. The carbon atoms in the propyl chains and most of the CF_3 groups of the [hfacac]⁻ ligands were refined isotropically. The $-\text{O}$ Propyl chains with O2 and O12 are also disordered and have been modelled over site occupancies of 65:35%. The CF_3 groups with C28, C29, C33 and C43 are disordered and each has been modelled over sites of 60:40%.

Figure S80. The structure of the asymmetric unit in $[\text{Cu}_3(\text{hfacac})_6(\mathbf{5})_2]_n$, with symmetry generated atoms. Hydrogen atoms are omitted for clarity; ellipsoids are plotted at 50% probability level. Symmetry codes: i = $-x, 1-y, -z$; ii = $-1+x, y, -1+z$; iii = $1-x, -y, 1-z$; iv = $-x, 1-y, -z$; v = $1-x, 1-y, 1-z$. The CF_3 groups with C27, C32 and C38 were refined isotropically and are also disordered; they have been modelled over sites of 75:25%, 70:30% and 70:30% occupancies, respectively, and only the major occupancy site is shown. The $-\text{OPentyl}$ chain containing O2 suffers from a *positional* disorder and has been modelled over sites of 75:25% occupancies.

Figure S81. Overlay of the experimental (blue) PXRD (298 K) for the bulk material and that predicted (black) from the single crystal structure (150 K) of $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{hfacac})_4(\mathbf{2})_2]_n \cdot 1.5n\text{CHCl}_3 \cdot 4n\text{MeOH}$.

Figure S82. Overlay of the experimental (blue) PXRD (298 K) for the bulk material and that predicted (black) from the single crystal structure (150 K) of $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{hfacac})_4(\mathbf{2})]_n \cdot 1.2n\text{CHCl}_3$.

Figure S83. The structure of the asymmetric unit in $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{hfacac})_4(\mathbf{2})_2]_n \cdot 1.5n\text{CHCl}_3 \cdot 4n\text{MeOH}$; ellipsoids are plotted at 50% probability level. Only the MeOH solvent molecules are shown.